

Imaginary Vacuums – 8T

"Ideas. I never memorize lines." Bobby Fischer

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equations of the new framework of variational manifolds, 8T, it is possible to expand the idea of the vacuum to include imaginary states of vacuum. Those state includes a higher summation of zeros, than "real" vacuums, which are null elements or minimal zeros. Each zero corresponds to prime pair vanishing; those pairs do not have an N_V element.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount, prime isomorphic, of curvature on the matric tensor. Those variations violate the condition of stationarity, causing fermion to cluster:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We derived the primorial by using total variations pairing, we searched for pairs that have certain features we know about fermions. In particular the total sums of the pairs had to be two and three divisible. Below marked in black and yellow are the pairings we used to derive the series.

$$\begin{aligned} &(3,3) (3,5) (3,7) (3,11), (3,13) \dots \\ &(5, 3) (5,5) (5,7) (5,11) \mathbf{(5, 13)} \dots \\ &(7, 3) (7,5) (7,7) \mathbf{(7, 11)} (7,13) \dots \\ &\dots \\ &(29, 19)(29,23), (29, 29), \mathbf{(29, 31)} \dots \end{aligned}$$

We calculated the sums of those prime pairing using the simple formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \mathcal{P}_i = S; \quad (2.14)$$

$$N = 2$$

And each of those pairs theorized based on theorem three, have a net curvature element proportional to the average, we searched for the first two pairs, derived the third coupling term using the formula of the primorial, without the prime pairing, and concluded the idea was correct.

$$(p_1, p_2) = (5, 13) \rightarrow N_V = +1$$

$$(p_3, p_4) = (29, 31) \rightarrow N_V = +3$$

$$(p_5, p_6) = (?, ?) \rightarrow N_V = +5$$

those prime pairs are in agreement with the coupling magnitudes does not mean that those pairs are exclusive or special. There is no law suggesting that these are the only pairs appearing in our theory and that is a good thing. Therefore, all prime pairing are appearing but because we have the condition of (1.48) those prime pairs of variations are taken to vanish. Therefore, we can define the prime pairs that are not suitable for the coupling criteria:

$$\begin{aligned} (p_N, p_{N+K}) &= S_N \\ S_N &\neq S \\ [2, 3] &| S \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

Assuming we required the original condition, for the sum to be divisible by two and three. Therefore, the majority of those pairs do not answer the condition. However since they still vanish due to being an even number and using equation, each pair could be regarded as a single distinct zero. So those prime pairs vanishing are the playing the rule of the vacuum in the 8T.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{N=7}^{\infty} (p_N, p_{N+K}) &\rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^T 0_i \\ T &\rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

We started the summation as the primes indexed from one to six does answer the criteria of coupling constants, and cannot be regarded as part of the vacuum. That is because they have a non-vanishing element N_V of certain kind. Those N_V elements are violations of stationarity causing fermions to cluster. The idea was presented in the canonical equations of curvature spikes, (1.8) for fermions and (1.81) for Bosons, vanishing and non-vanishing curvature spikes accordingly:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\delta g_i} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial g_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{g}_i} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0 \tag{1.8}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\delta g_i} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial g_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{g}_i} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) > 0 \tag{1.81}$$

The summation of the prime pairing to zero is resulting in an infinite set of zeros. That is synonymous with the vacuum idea of quantum field theory:

$$\sum_{i=1}^T 0_i = \mathcal{V} \tag{2.16}$$

The vacuum is the result of prime pairing which do not have a net variation element, as they are not sums identical to (2.15) in their devisors. Thus, they vanish into zero. The sum of all vanishing zeros is the vacuum of the 8T, as presented in equation (2.16). All prime pairs appear, as previously mentioned, we can pair any even number of primes, we chose $N = 2$ for simplicity sake. The idea of the vacuum in this theory is somewhat hard to grasp, as it requires knowing beforehand where those violations of stationarity will appear, which is impossible to know. What is possible to know is those violations of stationarity **has appeared**, that is simple, where there is stars and galaxies. The vacuum idea than is more appropriate to describe in terms of short to infinitesimal time intervals, it is not a continuous entity in time.

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T ideas that were presented in previous paper about the vacuum and in the 8T thesis, pages 143-144. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Suppose we want to classify vacuum states, which criteria do we should use? One idea is to classify the number of zeros appearing in the summation. Real vacuum should have minimal or null zeros, in the summation. Each zero correspond to a prime pair of certain sort which do not have a non-vanishing element, N_V , namely all the pairs excluding those who are marked in yellow black. A real vacuum state is the one possess least to null zeros. If a set of vacuum states were partitioned onto a set of distinct sets, each isomorphic to a unique summation:

$$\mathcal{V}_1 = [0_1, \dots 0_A]$$

...

$$\mathcal{V}_K = [0_1, \dots 0_Z]$$

In addition, all the partitioned sets are counted, the set with the smallest zero counts is the real vacuum and the rest are imaginary vacuum states. It is somewhat easier to analyze using the 8T and set partitioned than the ideas presented in QFT theories, which uses different mathematical tools. The second main point, The fact that those vacuums are composed by a set of zeros, does not indicate zero energy. The prime pair vanishing is, as the author believes release certain amount of energy, in the process of vanishing into zero. Those vacuum states do encompass energy. The question of how much energy is more complicated as it involves knowing two parameters;

- (1) The first is how many zeros in the partitioned set.
- (2) To which vanishing prime pairs those zeros corresponds. Larger prime pairs encompass more energy.

Those two demands imposes a real restriction regarding classification of real to imaginary vacuum states. We may never be able to know. Another possible complication is that the zeros can be varying from set to set, or alternatively put, merged together. So to minimal vacuums now, merged, will be now classified as imaginary vacuum, the number of zeros increased by twice. If \mathcal{V}_1 is the real, and \mathcal{V}_K is the imaginary, and they differ by additional zero, if the two minimal vacuums are merged, now they reversed the roles. \mathcal{V}_K is the real and $2\mathcal{V}_1$ is imaginary.

$$\mathcal{V}_1 + \mathcal{V}_1 > \mathcal{V}_K$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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